

Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2024-PF-01

(MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2024)

Topic: HORIZON-MSCA-2024-PF-01-01

Type of Action: HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-PF-EF

(HORIZON TMA MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships - European Fellowships)

Proposal number: 101202482

Proposal acronym: MOST-Cat

Type of Model Grant Agreement: HORIZON Unit Grant

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2	Participants	
3	Budget	
4	Ethics and security	
5	Other questions	

Application forms

Proposal ID **101202482**

Acronym **MOST-Cat**

1 - General information

Fields marked * are mandatory to fill.

Topic	HORIZON-MSCA-2024-PF-01-01	Type of Action	HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-PF-EF
Call	HORIZON-MSCA-2024-PF-01	Type of Model Grant Agreement	HORIZON-AG-UN

Acronym MOST-Cat

Proposal title

Note that for technical reasons, the following characters are not accepted in the Proposal Title and will be removed: < > " &

Scientific Area

Please select up to 5 descriptors (and at least 3) that best characterise the subject of your proposal, in descending order of relevance.

Descriptor 1

Descriptor 2

Descriptor 3

Descriptor 4

Descriptor 5

Free keywords

Please choose the scientific area and descriptors carefully, and in order of importance, since this will guide the REA in the selection of experts for proposal evaluation and the allocation of proposals to experts.

Application forms

Proposal ID **101202482**

Acronym **MOST-Cat**

Abstract *

The MOST-Cat project aims to advance in the field of Molecular Solar Thermal (MOST) systems by developing innovative heterogeneous catalysts, addressing the critical challenges of solar energy storage and release. Thus, utilizing transition metal complexes (TMCs) such as Co(II), Ni(II), and Cu(II) as catalytic moiety and metal oxides nanomaterials (MO; M=Si, Fe) as supports (e.g. SiO₂, Fe_xO_y, and double-shell SiO₂@Fe_xO_y), the project plans to synthesize and characterize a new generation of hybrid nanomaterials (TMC@MO), focusing on their catalytic performance in releasing the solar energy stored by MOST systems.

The innovative aspects of hybrid TMC@MO nanomaterials design are:

i) Formation of the TMC-MO covalent bond using alkoxysilane groups, limiting the phenomenon of catalyst leaching, facilitating solution purification, and preventing metal contamination.

ii) Development of various platforms combined with different TMCs allows for the generation of a wide range of heterogeneous catalysts, evaluating which parameters (surface area, morphology, TMC/nature load, etc.) are essential to maximize the catalytic performance of the final materials.

iii) Potential use of alternative sustainable catalysts (Ni(II) or Cu(II) TMCs) compared to traditional Co(II) TMCs.

The research activities will involve the synthesis and characterization of TMCs, MOs, and hybrid TMC@MO nanomaterials. Techniques like sol-gel synthesis and template-assisted methods will control MO solid-state features, crucial for optimizing catalytic efficiency. Additionally, the synthesized hybrid catalysts will be evaluated in innovative MOST systems to assess their effectiveness in promoting solar energy release, including studies of catalytic mechanisms using experimental techniques and theoretical calculations. Overall, the MOST-Cat project seeks to enhance MOST systems efficiency and sustainability while reducing the ecological impact of energy production.

Remaining characters

50

Has this proposal (or a very similar one) been submitted in the past 2 years in response to a call for proposals under any EU programme, including the current call?

Yes No

Please give the proposal reference or contract number.

Previously submitted proposals should be with either 6 or 9 digits.

Manage proposal

Deadline

11 September 2024 17:00:00 Brussels Local Time

Closed

Call data

Call: **HORIZON-MSCA-2024-PF-01**

Topic: **HORIZON-MSCA-2024-PF-01-01**

Type of action: **HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-PF-EF**

Type of MGA: **HORIZON-AG-UN**

Proposal data

Acronym: **MOST-Cat**

Draft ID: **SEP-211067984**

Final ID: **101202482**

Your proposal was submitted on: **03 September 2024 16:45:51 (Brussels Local Time)**

Your proposal is part of call **HORIZON-MSCA-2024-PF-01**. The call deadline is 11 September 2024 17:00:00 (Brussels Local Time).

Your proposal ID is **101202482**. This number is important and will be used as future reference during the evaluation process.

Revisit your proposal

The facility to re-edit is not available.

[Update proposal](#)

You may download a digitally signed and time-stamped version of your submitted proposal.

[Download](#)

The facility to withdraw is not available.

[Withdraw proposal](#)

HORIZON

Call: ERC-2025-STG

(Call for Proposals for ERC Starting Grant)

Topic: ERC-2025-STG

Type of Action: HORIZON-ERC

Proposal number: 101219316

Proposal acronym: FPNM-BioPC

Type of Model Grant Agreement: HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based

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Application forms

Proposal ID **101219316**

Acronym **FPNM-BioPC**

1 - General information

Fields marked * are mandatory to fill.

Topic	ERC-2025-STG	Type of Action	HORIZON-ERC
Call	ERC-2025-STG	Type of Model Grant Agreement	HORIZON-AG

Acronym FPNM-BioPC

Proposal title

Note that for technical reasons, the following characters are not accepted in the Proposal Title and will be removed: < > " &

Duration in months*

Primary ERC Review Panel*

Secondary ERC Review Panel

(if applicable)

ERC Keyword 1*

Please select, if applicable, the ERC keyword(s) that best characterise the subject of your proposal in order of priority.

ERC Keyword 2

ERC Keyword 3

ERC Keyword 4

Free keywords

Application forms

Proposal ID **101219316**

Acronym **FPNM-BioPC**

Abstract *

Photocatalysts (PCs) are compounds that drive electron or energy transfer from photo-excited states, playing an essential role in applications like CO₂ transformation, H₂ production, and various other catalytic processes. Among these, metal oxide (MO_x) have garnered attention for their exceptional photocatalytic performance in a wide range of chemical processes due to their ability to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) under light exposure. However, a significant drawback of semiconductor materials is their wide electronic bandgap, which limits their absorption to the UV component of sunlight, restricting their use for visible light-based applications. To overcome this issue, transition metal complexes or organic dyes that absorb in the visible region have incorporated into MO_x structure, as they can participate in the electron transfer (ET) process responsible for ROS generation. However, their high cost, low abundance, and potential toxicity drive the search for solutions. In this context, fluorescent proteins (FPs) present a promising bio-sustainable alternative due to their broad light absorption/emission range, non-toxic nature, and, moreover, their ability to generate photoinduced ET processes and ROS production. However, FPs face challenges such as rapid denaturation outside physiological conditions. FPNM-BioPC project aims to address these limitations by developing hybrid FP-based semiconductor nanomaterials through covalent bonding of FPs to MO_x, which guarantees protein stability and efficient ET processes/ROS production responsible for their catalytic activity. These biogenic functional materials will not only stabilize FPs but will also harness their potential to generate ROS under visible light, opening the door to a new class of sustainable PCs. By demonstrating their effectiveness in photodegrading persistent water pollutants, I will provide the transformative solutions for environmental remediation, setting new benchmarks in green chemistry.

Remaining characters

5

Has this proposal (or a very similar one) been submitted in the past 2 years in response to a call for proposals under any EU programme, including the current call?

Yes No

Please give the proposal reference or contract number.

Previously submitted proposals should be with either 6 or 9 digits.

Manage proposal

 Deadline
15 October 2024 17:00:00 Brussels Local Time

Closed

Call data

Call: **ERC-2025-STG**
Topic: **ERC-2025-STG**
Type of action: **HORIZON-ERC**
Type of MGA: **HORIZON-AG**

Proposal data

Acronym: **FPNM-BioPC**
Draft ID: **SEP-211082759**
Final ID: **101219316**

✔ Your proposal was submitted on: **09 October 2024 17:44:49 (Brussels Local Time)**

Your proposal is part of call **ERC-2025-STG**. The call deadline is 15 October 2024 17:00:00 (Brussels Local Time).

Your proposal ID is **101219316**. This number is important and will be used as future reference during the evaluation process.

Revisit your proposal

The facility to re-edit is not available.

[Update proposal](#)

You may download a digitally signed and time-stamped version of your submitted proposal.

[Download](#)

The facility to withdraw is not available.

[Withdraw proposal](#)

03.09.2024

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft
PED
Kennedyallee 40
53175 Bonn

Erklärung zum Antrag vom 26.08.2024 / Compliance Form: Proposal dated 2024-08-26

Vorgangsnummer / Transaction Number: 20240903314450036802

Antragstyp / Type of Proposal: Walter Benjamin-Programme - New Proposal/Establishment Proposal
Titel: Fluoreszierende Protein-Titandioxid-Nanomaterialien: Eine nachhaltige Zukunft für fortschrittliche fotoinduzierte Anwendungen
Title: Fluorescent Protein Titania Oxide NanoMaterials: a Sustainable Future for Advanced Photo-induced Applications
Antragsverantwortliche Person(en)/ Applicants: Dr. Mattia Nieddu Ph.D.
Fach / Subject Area: Solid State and Surface Chemistry, Material Synthesis
Anlagen / Attachments: FP-TiO2NM-Walter Benjamin.pdf
CV_List Publications.pdf
Employer Declaration.pdf
Adv Materials Technologies - 2024 - Chowdhury - Knocking the Stability of Solar Cells with Fluorescent Protein Donors upon.pdf
Advanced Materials - 2024 - Gutiérrez-Armayor - Simple Sol-Gel Protein Stabilization toward Rainbow and White Lighting.pdf
Advanced Science - 2023 - Nieddu - Core Shell Structured Fluorescent Protein Nanoparticles New Paradigm Toward.pdf
Contract MSCA.pdf
Contract Post-Doc.pdf
Letter of intent JCL_signed.pdf
Letter of recommendation JP.pdf

Hiermit bestätige ich, dass ich den oben genannten Antrag in elektronischer Form bei der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) eingereicht habe sowie die Richtigkeit der darin enthaltenen Angaben.

The undersigned herewith certify that they have submitted the proposal listed above electronically to the DFG and that the information contained therein is accurate.

Mattia Nieddu

Datum/Date

Ort/City

Unterschrift/Signature

English text see below

Mit der Einreichung eines Antrags bei der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)

verpflichten sich alle Antragstellerinnen und Antragsteller

- die **Grundsätze der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis** einzuhalten. Die Verfahrensordnung zum Umgang mit wissenschaftlichem Fehlverhalten (VerfOwF) findet Anwendung.
- die **Regeln zu den Publikationsverzeichnissen und zum Literaturverzeichnis** bei der Antragstellung zu beachten.
- jede Änderung gegenüber den Angaben in diesem Formular sofort der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft mitzuteilen.
- sämtliche für das Projekt einschlägigen Gesetze sowie sonstige projektbezogenen Vorschriften zu beachten und insbesondere eventuell erforderliche Genehmigungen rechtzeitig einzuholen.
- bei Arbeiten in Deutschland insbesondere
 - bei der Planung und Durchführung von **Versuchen an Menschen**, an identifizierbarem menschlichem Material und an identifizierbaren Daten insbesondere das Embryonenschutzgesetz, das Stammzellgesetz, das Arzneimittelgesetz, das Medizinproduktegesetz sowie die Deklaration von Helsinki in der jeweils geltenden Fassung einzuhalten, letzteres auch im in der Deklaration geforderten Umfang bei Arbeiten im Ausland.
 - zur Einhaltung der Vorschriften des Tierschutzgesetzes sowie der Versuchstierverordnung.
 - zur Einhaltung der Vorgaben des Gentechnikgesetzes im Rahmen von Versuchen mit gentechnisch veränderten Organismen (GVO).
- im Bewilligungsfall die volle Arbeitskraft auf das Forschungsvorhaben zu konzentrieren.
- die bewilligten Mittel ausschließlich im Interesse einer zielstrebigem Verwirklichung des geförderten Vorhabens einzusetzen, die einschlägigen Verwendungsrichtlinien der DFG zu beachten und insbesondere keine Grundausrüstung zu finanzieren.
- der DFG zu den im Bewilligungsschreiben angegebenen Terminen über den Fortgang der Arbeiten zu berichten und Nachweise über die Verwendung der bewilligten Mittel vorzulegen.
- keine weitere deckungsgleiche Förderung aus Mitteln deutscher Wissenschaftsförderung in Anspruch zu nehmen, sowie in Falle des Stipendiums sonstige deckungsgleiche Förderungen (z. B. durch ausländische Institutionen), jede sonstige Fremdfinanzierung wie auch jede für die Höhe des Stipendiums relevante Veränderung der persönlichen und/oder wirtschaftlichen Verhältnisse der DFG unverzüglich mitzuteilen.
- die DFG unverzüglich zu benachrichtigen, wenn ein Antrag auf Finanzierung dieses Vorhabens bei einer anderen Stelle eingereicht wird. Bereits an anderer Stelle eingereichte Anträge sind in der "Beschreibung des Vorhabens".
- und – sofern zutreffend –
 - bei Vorhaben mit möglichen sicherheitsrelevanten Aspekten ("Dual-Use Research of Concern") das Risiko-/Nutzen-Verhältnis abzuwägen und Maßnahmen zur Risikominimierung einzuplanen.
 - die Vertrauensdozentin bzw. den Vertrauensdozenten ihrer Hochschule von der Antragstellung zu unterrichten.

Ich/Wir akzeptiere/n alle oben stehenden Erklärungen und Verpflichtungen.

Die Inhalte der Verfahrensordnung zum Umgang mit wissenschaftlichem Fehlverhalten (VerfOwF) habe/n ich/wir zur Kenntnis genommen. Die VerfOwF erkenne/n ich/wir als für mich/uns verbindlich an.

Die DFG nimmt den Schutz Ihrer personenbezogenen Daten sehr ernst. Bitte beachten Sie die Datenschutzhinweise zur Forschungsförderung der DFG, die Sie unter www.dfg.de/datenschutz abrufen können. Bitte leiten Sie diese Hinweise auch an solche Personen weiter, deren Daten die DFG verarbeitet, weil sie in Ihrem Antrag aufgeführt sind.

Ich/Wir bestätige/n, die Datenschutzhinweise zur Kenntnis genommen zu haben.

English text:

In submitting this proposal to the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), all applicants agree to

- adhere to the **principles of good scientific practice**. The DFG's Rules of Procedure for Dealing with Scientific Misconduct (Verfahrensordnung der DFG zum Umgang mit wissenschaftlichem Fehlverhalten – VerfOwF) apply.
- have adhered to the **guidelines regarding publication lists and bibliographies**.
- inform the DFG immediately of any changes to the information provided.
- observe all relevant laws, regulations and guidelines that pertain to the project and in particular to attain all necessary approvals, certifications, etc., in a timely manner.
- for research in Germany in particular,
 - plan and conduct any **experiments involving humans**, including identifiable samples taken from

humans and identifiable data, in compliance with the most current versions of the German Embryo Protection Act (Embryonenschutzgesetz), Stem Cell Act (Stammzellgesetz), Pharmaceutical Drugs Act (Arzneimittelgesetz), Medical Devices Act (Medizinproduktegesetz), and Declaration of Helsinki, **the latter also for research conducted abroad** to the extent required under the Declaration.

- adhere to the regulations and provisions of the Animal Protection Act (Tierschutzgesetz) and the Experimental Animals Ordinance (Versuchstierverordnung).
- adhere to the provisions of the Genetic Engineering Act (Gentechnikgesetz) with regard to experiments involving genetically modified organisms (GMO).
- devote the total working time to the research project, should a grant be awarded.
- use the grant exclusively and in a targeted manner to realise the funded project, conform to the relevant regulations of the DFG, and in particular not use the grant to finance core support.
- submit research progress reports according to the dates specified in the award letter and present financial accounts to the DFG detailing the use of funds.
- not accept funding from other German research organisations or, in the case of a fellowship, any other source (e.g. from foreign institutions) for the same project and to inform the DFG of any financial assistance received and of any relevant changes in personal and/or financial circumstances that may affect the fellowship amount.
- inform the DFG immediately if funding for this project is requested from a third party. Proposals previously submitted to a third party must be mentioned in the Project Description.
- and if applicable,
 - examine whether the proposed project involves dual use research of concern, and if so, to weigh the benefits of pursuing this work against the risks of potential misuse and to implement measures to minimise these risks.
 - inform their university's DFG liaison officer about the proposal submission.

I/We accept the declarations and obligations listed above.

I am/We are familiar with the content of the DFG's Rules of Procedure for Dealing with Scientific Misconduct (Verfahrensordnung der DFG zum Umgang mit wissenschaftlichem Fehlverhalten – VerfOWF) and understand and accept that these Rules of Procedure are legally binding for me/us.

The DFG takes the protection of your personal data very seriously. Please note the DFG's data protection notice on research funding, which can be downloaded at www.dfg.de/privacy_policy. Please forward this information to those individuals whose data will be processed by the DFG because they are mentioned in your proposal.

I/We have read the DFG's data protection notice.

Für die Bearbeitung des o.g. Antrages benötigt die Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft die Unterschriften aller oben aufgeführten Antragstellenden zu den genannten Verpflichtungen. Bei mehreren Antragstellenden können die Unterschriften gemeinsam auf dieser Erklärung zum Antrag abgegeben werden. Alternativ kann jede antragstellende Person eine Kopie dieser Erklärung gesondert unterschreiben.

Before this proposal can be processed, the DFG requires signatures from all applicants listed above certifying that they accept and will comply with the conditions and obligations as stated. Multiple applicants may sign and submit this form jointly; they may also submit a signed copy of this form separately.

Mattia Nieddu

Datum / Date

Ort / City

Unterschrift / Signature